

Reflections of Modern Racism and Racial Politics: A Study of Paul Beatty's *Slumberland*

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Abstract

The present research paper depicts racial issues and stereotyping of blacks in Paul Beatty's novel Slumberland. This novel reflects that racism has not completely eroded from the America society. Through the protagonist, Ferguson W. Sowell, Beatty portrays racial discrimination as characters suffer from racism and loss of identity. The novel emphasizes that people of colour are marginalized, victimized, demoralized, and oppressed in American society. It seems racism has disappeared in the United States of America, but it is still prevalent in the minds of Americans. Through various stereotypical images, blacks in American society are dehumanized and demoralized. Beatty reflects that there are many negative stereotypes against black Americans. So, the objective of the paper is to show the various challenges of black people in American society through the novel Slumberland.

Introduction

Modern racism developed in the USA after the civil rights movement. It is a form of prejudice against African-Americans. This term was introduced by John McConahay in 1981 in the literature to deal with group processes and intergroup relations. Modern racism is nowadays in the USA; a verbally expressed negative racial attitude against Blacks. The old-fashioned beliefs that Blacks are inferior were unacceptable after the civil rights movement. Modern racism is characterized by the belief in voting against Black political leaders and emphasizing the policies designed for Blacks. Another characteristic of contemporary racism is that it is learned through socialization. People acquire modern racist attitudes from parents, society and the media. The theory of modern racism demonstrates the powerful negative racial attitudes against Blacks underlying current U.S. racial politics. African-Americans, other minor ethnic group have to fight for equal distribution of political power in USA. They are underrepresented as are women in government offices. Racial politics refers to race relation issues in society. In politics it means the struggle of minor ethnic and racial group to get political representation.

Paul Beatty's third novel, *Slumberland*, is set in Germany. The book's protagonist is Ferguson W. Sowell, also known as D.J. Darcy, an African American. He arrived in Berlin from Los Angeles in the 1980s. He is searching for the famous saxophonist Charles Stones, known as 'the Schwa', to perfect his beat. In Berlin, Sowell works as a jukebox sommelier in a bar named Slumberland. At that time, the Berlin Wall divided Germany into East Germany and West Germany. The novel's German setting talks about the USA's controversial issues. There is an analogy between the division in Germany between East and West and the division between Blacks and Whites in the USA. Although in the United States, whites enjoy the privileges as in Germany, West Germans, like blacks, face racial discrimination in America, so East Germans face it in Germany. After the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989, it is racism going to end in Germany. However, the narrator is frustrated when he sees increased racism in post-wall Germany or the reunification of Germany. So, Sowell and the Schwa decide to build a wall not with concrete but with music.

At the novel's beginning, D.J. Darcy believes, "The Negro is now officially human (*Slumberland* 3)." The researcher, Rani, mentions, "Though the government has officially proclaimed the Negroes as humans, society does not march towards the same. The conventional notions of both the whites and blacks do not have any changes" (Rani 75). Everyone says so, but it does not matter whether anyone believes it. First, the narrator thinks the blacks are mediocre and mundane, like the rest of the species. He believes that race war and Blackness in the USA have ended. Today every black looks like someone. In his father's time, they were nigger, but now they look like Magic Johnson or Chris Rock. Finally, the narrator thinks they will be looked down upon with blithe difference, not pity or the disgust of the Freudian projection. The nigger wanted to be judged not by their skin colour but by the content of the character. In *Slumberland*, the narrator misses his Los Angeles days and his fear of that area. He adds that black man in the USA has many concerns like fear of the police, water, and the math section of the Scholastic Aptitude Test. Moving to Berlin has reduced his fear of being mistaken. Another worry the narrator discusses is identity, "But that fear of myself was who I was. It was all I and a lot of

other little Los Angelenos had" (Beatty 19). Beatty reveals the inherent problem of every black in America. Once, D J Darcy, the narrator, is called by the Los Angeles District School for special testing that frightens his parents. Because it was not long ago that men of colour were purposely infected with syphilis. In the novel, Paul Beatty tells the problem of identity and fear of black from the whites in the United States of America.

Ferguson W. Sowell once tells the incident when he was called to Los Angeles Unified School District for a math test. He wanted to be first in the class. Sowell dictates discrimination against the blacks as the teacher asks him to sit in the back row. This row was occupied by two Sunday-suited black boys and a coloured girl in her mother's cut-down wedding dress. The test was conducted, and scores were posted outside the classroom in descending order. It was Sowell's first computer printout test. He could see his name at the top of the list written Ferguson W. Sowell: 100/100. When he was summoned to the office, the official denied Sowell's suitability for aeronautical and nuclear sciences. The official asks Sowell to keep the mechanical pencil. Beatty discloses the racial discrimination in America through his black character, who scored 100 out of 100 but is denied admission to the best course. The white students were admitted to an advanced mathematics class, but Negroes were sent to a musical academy.

The white students were placed in an advanced mathematics class at the university; we Negro boys, and the lone girl, were given instruments and sent to the Wilmer Jessop Academy of Music. I never saw Uukkarnit again. (*Slumberland* 19)

The narrator is not admitted to advanced mathematics due to his black race. Beatty depicts that African-Americans are discriminated against, but for the progress of America, the development of every person must be either black or white. W. E. B. Du Bois writes in *The Soul of Black Folk*, "In all things purely social, we can be as separate as the five fingers, and yet one as the hand in all things essential to mutual progress" (Bois 34). Du Bois states that the growth of America is possible if all are getting equal opportunities and treatment.

Every human wants his acceptance by others. It is in the form of respect, treating one another with smiles on their faces. However, Blacks do not enjoy this respect in society; they feel disconnected. D.J. Darcy also experiences the same disrespect in childhood but finds good treatment in Germany. He recalls his childhood memories which lead him to restlessness. Beatty writes in *Slumberland* thus,

I hadn't slept since I got to Berlin. Slumberland. The name itself was foreboding enough to keep me out. It brought back all the childhood traumas, the sleepless nights staring at the lighting-bolt-blue while pondering the relationship between reality, the dream state, and death. My father embittered literature Ph. D. Who worked for the county naming the streets within walled communities that sprouted up on Californian hillsides like concrete weeds, but did nothing to ease my fear of the dark and dying? (53)

Darcy here remarks on his fear of childhood when he was in America. He thinks of reality, how the state should have been and death. These are social and cultural inequality in the USA. His father worked for the community on California hillside that also did nothing to ease his fear of death and the dark. Beatty reveals that even though some American believes the country is post-racial, there is racism that his characters experience.

The postmodern cultural forms in society bring alienation, disorientation and invasion to society. The Africans have to struggle to safeguard their cultural heritage. Darcy has to battle for their culture. The racist in America considers themselves powerful to manipulate the marginalized in society. African-Americans cannot grow in America. Paul Beatty states.

This city, this country has been dead for a long, long time, and if somebody like Charles Stones is out there somewhere, it means the culture soil is no longer fallow. Picasso blossomed in Paris, and the city flowered along with him. Gauguin in Tahiti. Kerouac in Mexico. Erich Von Stroheim in Hollywood. D.J. Darcy and Charles Stone in Berlin. (100)

For blacks, America is not the right place. That is why all the blacks have been to somewhere else for success.

When he first meets East Germans after the fall of the Berlin Wall, D.J. Darcy cannot recognize them. He forgets about the previous division between East German and West German. To him, "They looked Germans, albeit with even tighter pants and uglier shoes, but there was something different about them. I figured maybe the Austrian national soccer team was in town or there was a kartoffelpuffer famine in Luxemburg" (Beatty 110). After the fall of the German Wall, East and West Germans came together like the blacks and the white in America after the end of the racial fence. With the Wall, the narrator remembers the blue Wall that LAPD is erecting at a disciplinary hearing held for officers who beat the narrator and Blaze, who were waiting silently for the bus. They were blamed for stealing a car. Beatty shows the racial discrimination in the novel between East and West Germans, but his main concern is racial discrimination between blacks and whites in America. Beatty says that by ending the racial Wall, black and whites are united, and East German and West Germans are united by finishing the Berlin Wall. These walls are still there in people's minds; until they are not removed, racial discrimination cannot be ended.

One day Doris, Lars, and the narrator went to an outdoor café. They were reading an English-language newspaper when Doris shouted at the paper's Berlin correspondent, David Levin. "I hate this old Jew! She shouted, backhanding the world section (*Slumberland* 136)." Doris felt East Germans were too biased and bitter

and Jewish and old. The narrator remembers that before reunification, no one called him nigger to his face or said Jew was pejorative. Now the people have started calling him 'Smokey.' According to D.J. Darky, racial tension in Germany has reached its peak. As a result of increased racism, people want the Wall back. The West Berliners like to feel good and unique living on an island in the middle of a landmass. Further in the novel, polls are held to bring the Wall back, and 20 per cent of people want it back (Schweinfurt 4). Beatty says racism has increased, so East and West Germans cannot unite. In the same way, in the USA, the race war between blacks and whites cannot be ended.

Paul Beatty exposes the falseness of monolithic and monotonous racial myth-making. The protagonist and narrator, Ferguson W. Sowell, aka D.J. Darky, an African-American, has a phonographic memory, i.e., he can learn every sound he has ever heard. "Don't they know that after fourteen hundred years; the charade of Blackness is over? He asks. "Everyone, even the British, says so." *Slumberland* is a novel of precisely this charade and a story of abused stereotypes and archetypes reclaimed. It delights in racial essentialism even as it decries and dismisses hipness using the hippest touchstone Beatty can lay his hand on. (Neate 2)

Sowell learns music from watching Spencer Tracey on Turner Classic Movies than from any composition class. He wants the perfect beat and is searching for Charles Stone, known as the Schwa, a little-known avant-garde jazz musician. Sowell used to score porn films. However, he becomes a jukebox sommelier when he discovers that D.J. and porno composers do not qualify as musicians or artists. Bridgette Lopez, a divorcee Sowell one thought to marry, tells him to go for a jukebox sommelier. So, he writes to Slumberland Bar in Berlin and requests them a position as a jukebox sommelier enclosing his resume. Two weeks later, he receives a letter stating his salary in the paper. One afternoon in Berlin, the narrator finds the outside full of unshakable faith in humankind. He does not find traffic, and the shops are closed. The narrator there asks an old lady about blacks, and we learn about the stereotyping against blacks. They are considered small-minded and stupid.

For fun, I'll ask the muttering old woman how she feels about Neger-Neger (Nigger-Niggers) like myself and she'll say, "Love them. Slept with a couple after the war. Nice boys. Polite. Big schwanze, small minds, and even tinier ears. Maybe that's why they are so stupid, they don't hear everything. (Beatty 110)

The narrator reminds the Restoration period of American history after the fall of the Berlin Wall. He is reminded of scalawags, carpetbaggers, and lynch mobs. The editorial warnings state that East Germans are lazy and can never assimilate the West Germans. The fall of the Berlin Wall is the beginning of a new era in which the narrator starts to feel German. Beatty compares the fall of the Berlin Wall and the Restoration period of American history not to show the racial tension between East and West Germans but to address the racial tension between black and whites in the United States of America. Through East Germans, Beatty shows whites' stereotypical images of blacks. African-Americans are considered lazy and unproductive citizens. Again, it is described that those minor cultures trying to assimilate the advanced culture is impossible. It will create conflict in their minds.

Germany Changed. After the Wall fell, it reminded me of the Restoration period of American history, There were the requisite whining editorials warning the public that assimilation was a dream, that the inherently lazy and shiftless East Germans would never be productive citizens. (*Slumberland* 134)

Paul Beatty portrays that Germany has changed. The East and the West Germans are reconciled, but there are cautions regarding this reunion. Dr Cornel West writes in *Race Matters*, "None of us alone can save the nation or world. But each of us can make a positive difference if we commit ourselves to do so" (109). In the novel, East and West Germans are united like blacks and whites in the USA. It is believed that America has become a post-racial America and is improving. Nevertheless, racial tension cannot be removed by making laws. However, West states that blacks and whites can make a positive difference and save the nation if committed.

Through the East Germans, Beatty points out African-Americans as lazy and idle. These are stereotypical images of blacks in America. They are considered unproductive citizens of the world. The Berlin Wall in the novel symbolizes the micro freedom ascribed to African-Americans. "In *Slumberland's* section titled "The Souls of Black Volk," we meet the Von Robinson sisters, Black East Germans who learn about African-American culture by reading Pushkin and listening to jazz on the *Voice of America* radio show: the title, a play on W. E. B. Du Bois's *The Souls of Black Folk* encapsulates the sisters' relationship with their homeland through their absent African-American G.I. father. Dispossessed of the richness of African-American culture but endowed with a sense of communist egalitarianism and strength, their double consciousness results in a kind of natural Blackness that protagonist D.J. Darky admires." (Hoagland 158)

Ferguson W. Sowell sees that racial tension has increased in Germany after the fall of the Berlin Wall. The country is more divided than ever, and the East Germans are treated as inferior and second-class citizens. Doris and Lars, the West Germans who visit East Germany, are very disappointed when they see the bullet-ridden buildings and ghastly mullet haircuts. They view East Germans as fundamentally different from themselves.

Lazy, unmotivated, and ungrateful. Every day they had a new joke about their backward fellow citizens:

Q: Why do East German policemen travel in threes?

A: One to read, one to write, and one to keep an eye on the two intellectuals. (Beatty 136)

Beatty reveals how the tension has grown between the East and West Germans. Through jokes, they show the lack of intelligence of East Germans. The West Germans treat the East Germans as lazy, unmotivated, and ungrateful. The West Germans have started to serve them as dehumanized. They demonstrate their superiority over East Germans and poke fun at them. Hence, Beatty says that the Berlin Wall is no longer in existence, but this racial bitterness is still in the minds of West Germans. J Emagulate Rani writes that the mental disability and the language of slavery have been used in the novel for blacks. The whites do not attack but verbally attack the Blacks. It is shameful to remind someone of their colour and ridicule him. The official turns blind to racism; that is why it is ingrained in society. The protagonist has to battle against stereotypical images of blacks. Blacks have a high potential of committing a crime as a prejudice. The provocative word in American society is racism. There is a belief to determine human qualities and capacities based on race is unfair. (Rani 101).

Conclusion

Slumberland highlights the pain and discrimination with blacks in American society. The characters confront racism and identity problems as they are deprived from their rights and values. The narrator D.J. Darky was deprived to progress in the studies. In this way, Beatty has discussed the various challenges of blacks in contemporary America. Fatima, an Afro-East German suffers from dehumanization as a result of which she finally commits suicide. Her fundamental rights are snatched as she has struggled for the identity and position in the American society.

References

- Abani, Chris. "Slumberland by Paul Beatty." *Los Angeles Times*, June 2018. <https://www.latimes.com/style/lb-ak-abani15-2008jun15-story.html>.
- Aggarwal, Aparna, Ahmad Naik, Gowher. "Narratives Of Indian Women And Their Catastrophes: A Study Of Geetanjali Shree's Tomb Of Sand." *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, vol, 6, no. 12, 2022, pp. 1735-1741.
- Beatty, Paul. *Slumberland*. One World, 2008.
- Benfer, Amy. "The Book Review: *Slumberland* by Paul Beatty." *Barnes & Noble Review*, July 2008. <https://www.barnesandnoble.com/review/slumberland>, Accessed 31 March 2020.
- Henry, P. J. "Modern racism." To appear in J. Levine & M. Hogg, *The Encyclopedia of group processes and intergroup relations*. Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks, CA, 2010, pp. 575-577.
- Hoagland, George. "Paul Beatty's *Slumberland* and Myth of Blackness." *Ethnic Literature and Transnationalism: Critical Imageries of a Global Age*, edited by Aparajita Nada, Routledge, 2015, pp. 145-158.
- Kumar, Sanjay and Gowher Ahmad Naik. "Race, Issues and Perspectives: A Critical Study of Its Genealogy." *Journal of Critical Reviews*, Volume 7, Issue 14, 2020, pp. 4240-4242.
- . "Stereotypical Images of Blacks in American Society: A Study of Paul Beatty's *The Sellout*." *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, Volume 12, Issue 10, 2021, pp. 359-362.
- Naik, Gowher Ahmad and Sanjay Kumar. "Misrecognition and Struggle For Identity of Blacks: A Study of Beatty's *The White Boy Shuffle* and *The Sellout*." *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, Volume 17, Issue 6, 2020, pp. 14863-14867.
- . "Analyzing Racial Discrimination and Slavery: The Study of Marlon James *The Book of Night Women*." *Shodh Sanchar Bulletin*, Volume 9, Issue 36, 2019, pp. 207-210.
- Neate, Patrick. "Review: *Slumberland* by Paul Beatty." *The Guardian*, December 2006. <https://www.theguardian.com/books/2008/dec/06/fiction-slumberland-paul-beatty-patrick-neate>, Accessed 31 July 2019.
- Rani, J. Emagulate. *Demystifying the Postmodern Panoramas in the Novels of Paul Beatty*. 2023, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirapalli, Ph.D. Dissertation. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/466684>.
- Kapur, Vanshika, Ahmad Naik, Gowher. "Racial Metamorphosis And Bigotry In Mohsin Hamid's *The Last White Man*." *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, vol, 6, no. 12, 2022, pp. 1758-1765.

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